
Navigating The Work Force: The Intersection of Emotional Intelligence and Working Women

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ABSTRACT:

Emotional intelligence is a tool used to understand and manage one's emotions. The major five aspects involved in emotional intelligence are self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy and social skills. Unfortunately, in the real sense none has got the ability to fully understand and tackle human emotions. It is very evident that emotional intelligence is beneficial both in and out of the workplace. So, the present study has been taken up to explore the emotional intelligence of working women at RIE Mysuru and to compare their emotional intelligence with respect to different work positions that they occupy. Descriptive study design has been employed with an intact group of 53 working women from different positions they occupy (i.e., school teachers, college teachers and non-teaching staffs) at RIE Mysuru. Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire from Leadership Toolkit has been adopted and it consists of 50 items which intended to get the information about self-awareness, managing emotions, motivating oneself, empathy and social skills from the target groups. The data collected have been qualitatively analysed by using percentage analysis. The results revealed that working women at RIE Mysuru have got good emotional intelligence and they develop higher emotional intelligence when they go up the ladder of the work positions. This research provides new and original context-specific insights on emotional intelligence among women; these findings can

be used as a basis for future research on emotional intelligence among women of different status while providing a knowledge base for contemporary emotional intelligence research.

KEYWORDS:

Emotional Intelligence, Working Women, Gender, Social Skill, Self-awareness.

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INTRODUCTION:

Emotional intelligence was formally defined by Salovey and Mayer (1990). They defined it as ‘the capacity to monitor one’s own and others’ feelings and emotions, to distinguish among them and to use this information to guide one’s thinking and actions. They also provided an initial empirical knowledge about how an aspect of emotional intelligence could be measured as a mental ability (Mayer, DiPaolo, & Salovey, 1990).

The term ‘emotional intelligence’ was not known to any researchers, practitioners and the society until Goleman (1995) wrote the best-selling book, *Emotional Intelligence: Why it can Matter More than IQ*. It is being widely believed by the people that emotional and social competence is more important compare to the traditional dimension of personality and intellectual ability (Goleman, 1995, 1998). Emotional intelligence is defined as “the constituent set of capabilities that enable an individual to manage himself/herself and to deal with others” (Goleman, 1995, 1998). “It is more accurate to state that the frequency with which an individual demonstrates or uses the composite capabilities or competencies, inherent in emotional intelligence to determine the ways in which he/she deals with themselves, their life, to cope with works and to get along with others” (Boyatzis, Goleman and Rhee, 2000).

Daniel Goleman found out that the traditional qualities that are associated with leadership such as vision, intelligence, determination and toughness are required to achieve success but they are insufficient. Truly proficient leaders are distinguished by a high degree of emotional intelligence, which includes:

- » **Self-awareness:** The ability to recognize one's own feeling, to understand their habitual emotional responses to events and to recognize one's emotions affect their behavior and performance. When they are self-aware, they can see themselves as others and have a good sense of their abilities and current limitations.
- » **Managing emotions:** The ability to stay focused and think clearly even if they are experiencing powerful emotions. Being able to manage one's own emotional state is crucial for taking responsibility for their own actions and can save them from taking hasty decisions that lead to regret later.
- » **Motivating oneself:** The ability to use one's deepest emotions to move and guide them towards their goals. This potential skill enables them to take the initiative and persist them to face obstacles and setbacks.
- » **Empathy:** The capability to sense, understand and respond to what other people are feeling. Self-awareness comes first in order to have empathy with others. If an individual is not aware of his/her own emotions, then he/she will not be able to read the emotions of others.
- » **Social Skills:** The capability to manage, influence and inspire emotions in others. Being able to handle emotions in relationships and being able to influence and inspire others are crucial foundation skills for successful teamwork and leadership.

Emotional Intelligence of Women at Workplace:

The idea of EQ and business was popularized by Daniel Goleman's influential article 'What Makes a Leader?', published in the 1998 Harvard Business Review. Goleman challenged the long-held belief that intellect and rationality are crucial to achieve success.

After reviewing the related literature, it has been found out that women obtained high scores in emotional intelligence compare to men (Barchard 2001; Meyer and Geher 1996; Mayer, Salovey, Caruso 2000a; Mayer, Salovey and Caruso 2000b). Few researches have shown that women are more emotionally intelligence than men (Beisecker and Barchard 2004). There are many tests of emotional intelligence available, and most of them seem to show that women tend to perform better than men when it comes to these basic skills for a happy and successful life. This matters more in the workplace, as all these potential skills can be utilized to attain higher position and leadership. On the other hand, it's not that simple. For instance, some researchers noted that women are on average compare to men at some forms of empathy. But sometimes men do stand better than women when it comes to managing distressing emotions. Whenever we talk about such behavioral gender differences, we are drawing two different conclusions, one for men and one for women that largely coincide.

Women, with their innate emotional intelligence, are particularly well equipped with the basic skill's necessary success. "Women tend to be better at emotional empathy than men, in general," Dr. Dan Goleman wrote in Psychology Today. "This kind of empathy fosters rapport and chemistry. People who excel in emotional empathy make good counselors, teachers and group leaders because of this ability to sense in the moment how others are reacting."

Based on the above-mentioned statements, the current study was conducted to explore the emotional intelligence of

working women from different positions they occupy at RIE Mysuru.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS:

- What is the emotional intelligence of working women at RIE Mysuru?
- Does the emotional intelligence of working women differ with the different positions they occupy?

OBJECTIVES:

- To study the emotional intelligence of working women at RIE Mysuru.
- To compare the emotional intelligence of working women from different positions they occupy at RIE Mysuru.

METHODOLOGY:

The present study employed descriptive study design which explore the emotional intelligence of working women at RIE Mysuru and to compare their emotional intelligence with respect to different work positions that they occupy. This study included an intact group of 53 working women from different positions they occupy (i.e., school teachers, college teachers and non-teaching staffs) at RIE Mysuru. Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire from Leadership Toolkit has been adopted for the present study to explore the emotional intelligence of working women. The questionnaire consists of 50 items which intended to get the information about self-awareness, managing emotions, motivating oneself, empathy and social skills from the target groups.

DATA ANALYSIS:

The present study revealed the total percentage of emo-

tional intelligence of working women and the difference in emotional intelligence of working women from different positions they occupy (i.e., school teachers, college teachers and non-academic staffs) at RIE Mysuru. It has been qualitatively analysed by using percentage analysis.

Research Question-1

What is the emotional intelligence of working women at RIE Mysuru?

To answer the above research question the following table was used.

Table 1. Descriptive analysis of emotional intelligence of working women at RIE Mysuru.

	Strength	Needs Attention	Development Priority
Self-awareness	45%	39%	16%
Managing emotions	14%	54%	32%
Motivating oneself	43%	35%	22%
Empathy	20%	56%	24%
Social skills			50%

Research Question-2

Does the emotional intelligence of working women differ with the different positions they occupy?

To answer the above research question the following table was used.

Table 2. Descriptive analysis of emotional intelligence of working women from different positions they occupy at RIE Mysuru.

	College Teachers			School Teachers			Non-teaching Staffs		
	S	NA	DP	S	NA	DP	S	NA	DP
Self-awareness	66%	17%	17%	38%	52%	10%	30%	40%	30%
Managing emotions	17%	58%	25%	10%	60%	30%	8%	47%	45%
Motivating oneself	59%	25%	16%	40%	55%	5%	19%	38%	43%
Empathy	34%	50%	16%	20%	61%	19%	19%	50%	31%
Social skills	59%	33%	8%	33%	57%	10%	26%	40%	34%

INTERPRETATION OF DATA:

Out of the 53 working women from RIE Mysuru, 45% of them have got highest scores in self-awareness; 43% of them are good at in motivating oneself and 50% of them are excellent in social skills. More than half of the women show average concern towards managing emotions and empathy (i.e., 54% and 56% respectively).

Out of the 3 different work positions of women at RIE Mysuru, college teachers have scored highest in all the 5 categories (i.e., Self-awareness, managing emotions, Motivating oneself, Empathy and Social skills) of Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire. School teachers have scored highest in average column of these categories and they need attention to develop emotional intelligence. Compared to above 2 positions, the non-teaching staffs have scored highest in below average column of these categories and they should give high priority to develop emotional intelligence. In total it has found that, emotional intelligence of the working women increased with the increase in the working positions of the women at RIE Mysuru.

CONCLUSION:

The findings of the study add to the fact that working

women have got good emotional intelligence and they develop higher emotional intelligence when they go up the ladder of the work positions. It's clear that large percentage of the working women are emotionally intelligent but they need to take more time to self-assess and work on their emotions. Like anything, you need practice, but even small steps can make a huge difference.

Emotional intelligence of women can enhance good relationships, building skills and career advancement. Additionally, empathy fosters healthy workplace relationships. Emotional Intelligence also helps to understand ineffective emotion regulations like tension & conflict, control, avoidance, resistance and increase self-awareness, self-reflection & resiliency. To make emotional intelligence effective, you need to start with yourself. So, learning how to cope with emotional intelligence could lead to great success. This research provides new and original context-specific insights on emotional intelligence among women; these findings can be used as a basis for future research on emotional intelligence among women of different status while providing a knowledge base for contemporary emotional intelligence research.

REFERENCES:

1. Goleman, D. (1998). Working with emotional intelligence. New York: Bantam Books.
2. Boyatzis, R. E., D. Goleman, K. & Rhee. (2000). Clustering competence in emotional intelligence: insights from the Emotional Competence Inventory (ECI). In R. Bar-On and J. D. A. Parker (Eds), Handbook of Emotional Intelligence. San Francisco. Jossey Bars
3. Bhatti, A. G. (2013). An analysis of the general and gender difference regarding emotional intelligence among employees: evidence from government and nongovernment organizations of Hyderabad. KASBIT Business Journal, 6:106-113
4. Mayer, C-H., Oosthuizen, R.M., & Surtee, S. (2017). Emotional intelligence in South African women leaders in higher education. SA Journal of Industrial Psychology/SA Tydskrif vir Bedryfsielkunde, 43(0), a1405. <https://doi.org/10.4102/sajip.v43i0.1405>
5. Meshkat, M., & Nejadi, R. (2017). Does Emotional Intelligence Depend on Gender? A Study on Undergraduate English Majors of Three Iranian Universities. SAGE Open. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244017725796>
6. Khanam, N., Sahu, T, Rao, E. V., Gaidhane, A. (2018). A study on various dimensions of emotional intelligence among doctors. International Journal Community Med Public Health, 5:390-4.

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Conflict of interest:

The Authors have no conflict of interest to declare that they are relevant to the content of this article.

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